

Local Government in India

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in India

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Types of Local Governments

In India, institutions of local government exist at two levels, local *panchayats* or councils in the rural areas and municipalities in the urban areas. At the rural level, *Panchayati Raj* Institutions (PRIs) consist of three levels: *gram panchayats*, *panchayat samitis* and *zilla parishads*.

A *gram panchayat* can be translated as village council or jury as it is the only grassroots-level institution of PRIs' formalized local self-governance system in India at the village or small-town level. It consists of an elected *sarpanch* (head) and five to twelve elected members. The *gram panchayats* are responsible for the creation of annual development plans, the budget for construction, repairs and maintenance of community assets, *khadi* and village industries¹, adult and non-formal education, public health, poverty alleviation, education, cultural activities, rural housing and electrification, promoting agriculture, social welfare and public distribution scheme.

At the intermediate level, the *panchayat samitis* (block panchayats) operate. They work at the *tehsil* or *taluka* level² known as development block and provide a crucial link of communication between *gram panchayat* and district administration. They are also known as *mandal parishad*,

¹ Village and *khadi* industries are based on the concept of *Swadeshi* wherein the use of labour is central and the use of capital is limited, underlying the concept of self-reliance in the economy. These industries rely on local raw materials and local production at small scale.

² There are two constitutional amendments, 73rd and 74th passed in 1992 which provide a whole scenario of the different levels of local governments at rural and urban level. The 73rd amendment states a three-tier system of *panchayati raj* at the village *panchayat* (*gram*), block (intermediate) level (*panchayat samiti*) and district levels (*zilla parishad*) for a population of more than 20 lakh (2 million). *Gram* or village *panchayat* consists of *gram sabha* and members of the village *panchayat* directly elected by the people and headed by the *pradhan* (elected head) village council (*gram sabha*) consist of all the members of the village. Each *gram panchayat* is assisted by four committees that is *samata samiti* (committee for welfare of women and children, scheduled caste and tribes and other backward classes) *vikas samiti* (committee for development in agriculture), *shiksha samiti* (education) and *lokhit* committee (public health and public works). In between *gram panchayat* and *zilla panchayat* is *panchayat samiti* (committee) which forms the main chain of communication between the two. The next level of local government is *zilla parishad*, consisting of all the elected representatives of *gram panchayat* and elected representatives from territorial constituencies in the panchayat, members of legislative assembly and legislative council

The 74th Amendment consists of three bodies of urban governments – *nagar panchayat* which is primarily constituted when the village transitions from rural to urban, municipal council for smaller urban areas, municipal corporations for larger urban areas. Municipal committees are also assisted by ward committees which makes a two-tier system.

mandal panchayat and *taluka panchayat* and are primarily made of four-member ex officio bodies bringing together all *sarpanchas* of the development block, the members of parliament (MPs) and MLAs (members of legislative assembly) of the area, and sub-divisional officer (SDOs).³ The functions of the *panchayat samitis* are agricultural and land improvement, establishment of primary health centers and primary schools, water and sanitation, village infrastructure (construction of roads etc.), establishment of cooperative societies, water and irrigation management, promotion of animal husbandry, dairy and poultry, social welfare, social activities, technical training, poverty alleviation, promotion and development of cottage and skill industries.

The third level is the *zilla parishad* (district council). *Zilla parishad* or the district council is an elected body consisting of members from state legislatures and the Parliament as explained later. The ex officio chief executive officer of the *zilla parishad* is the additional deputy commissioner who is either from the Indian Administrative Services (IAS) or Provincial Civil Services (PCS) appointed in the state. The *zilla parishad* consists of mainly elected members from demarcated constituencies, the chairpersons of *panchayat samitis*, MPs and MLAs. The member of the *zilla parishad* also acts as chairperson of the *parishads* (councils) that fall in their constituencies from which they are elected for a term of five years. The functions of the *zilla parishad* are planning and administration of development projects for the district, delivery of services and facilities to the village, promotion of agricultural projects such as training new techniques of farming, horticulture, rural housing, electrification, animal husbandry and dairy, promotion of small-scale industries, health and hygiene, education and social welfare. In all the levels of local governments, there are reserved seats for women, scheduled caste, scheduled tribes and other backward classes.

All the institutions of local self-government operate under the principle of democratic decentralization. The rationale of democratic decentralization was to create PRIs in a multi-level framework of governance which are autonomous, democratic and financially strong. It was a step away from a top-down approach to local governance in order to provide self-administration to people in the rural areas. The twenty-nine functions and responsibilities of the PRIs which have been stated above are all enshrined in the Indian Constitution in the Article 243G. The functions are listed in the eleventh Schedule of the Constitution.

At the urban level, there are three types of local bodies, the *nagar nigam* (municipal corporation), *nagar palika* (municipality) and *nagar panchayat* (town *panchayat*). The status of an area decides the provision and implementation of urban local bodies. For an area transitioning from rural to urban, a city council is required. In small urban areas a municipality

³ The districts in a state are divided into sub-divisions and the sub-divisional officer (SDOs) oversees these divisions. The SDO is responsible for the administration of these divisions in the districts. There can be two kinds of roles. One in which they are in charge of office work and another, in which they are not bound in an office but are overseeing a range of works such as communicating with people, overlooking implementation of government schemes.

is required and in large urban areas a municipal corporation.⁴ The functions and powers of urban local bodies vary from state to state. Municipal corporations work and directly interact with the state governments. The head of the corporation is the mayor and the principal executive officer is the municipal commissioner. Municipalities interact with the respective state government through the district collector. The head of the municipality is the president elected by the members of the *palika*. The state government appoints officers such as health or sanitation Inspectors to provide assistance to the president. City councils have a chairman and ward members. The functions assigned to urban local bodies are urban planning and management, provision of health services, education, water management, waste disposal and sanitation, public infrastructure, birth and death registrations, poverty alleviation and delivery of social services.

Legal Status of Local Governments

To realize the goals of democratic decentralization, the government amended the Constitution and passed the 73rd and 74th Amendment Act in 1992. The important aspects of the act were the three-tier system of *panchayati raj* for all states exceeding the population of two millions, the holding every five years of *Panchayat* elections, the reservation of seats for women, scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, the appointment of a state finance commission to make recommendations in cognizance with the financial powers of the panchayat and the establishment of district planning committees (DPCs) to prepare development plans for the district as a whole. It also foresaw the establishment of a state election commission to help state governments conducting periodic elections to the PRIs. Similarly, for urban local governments, the 74th Amendment provides a three-tier structure of governance with the municipal wards as the territorial constituencies forming the basic unit of urban local governance.

The scope of powers and functions enshrined in the Constitution envision PRIs to function as institutions of local self-government and to operationalize the devolution of powers which is central to the principle of democratic decentralization. The scope and powers entrusted to PRIs base themselves in the ideals of economic development and social justice. In accordance with the constitutional amendment, the state governments repealed the then existing acts. The 73rd Amendment Act was further extended to the scheduled areas and areas predominantly occupied with tribal population. It was extended through the provisions of *Panchayat Extension to Scheduled Areas Act, 1996*.

⁴ Transitioning areas are defined based on how fast a town is developing due to industrialization or agricultural growth or secondary services. The criteria of population and the level of administrative functions is considered too, as big cities such as Delhi, Mumbai and others will have a municipal corporation and smaller towns will have municipalities.

For the urban local bodies, 74th Amendment Act was adopted in 1992 enjoining the government of the day to ensure continuity of the municipalities through a periodic five-year election. Similar to the *Panchayati Raj* System, the urban local bodies have a three-tier system, including the above-mentioned municipal corporations, municipalities and town *panchayats*. The composition of these councils is decided by state governments respectively. There are reservations of seats for women, scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and other backward classes.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

The rural and urban government bodies do not have exactly similar scopes of responsibilities. The former are more entrusted with tasks of being regulators, administrators and providers of various services at the local level. The latter have two sets of parts to play. One, the municipal corporation must deliberate on matters related to budget, taxation, pricing of services and others, and two, the municipal commissioner is the executive head and exercises control on various departments such as finance, health etc. For example, the urban local bodies have to look at the jurisdictional domain of various urban areas, their judicial powers, implementation of policies and plans as per the 74th Constitutional Amendment. Despite their differences regarding modes of functioning and the devolution of the powers and authority, both rural and urban local bodies aim at enabling people's participation as a sign of democratic citizenship.

Political and Social Context in India

India has a multiparty parliamentary system of democracy with representatives at the local, state and national levels contesting elections and participating in democratic decision-making process. Both national and state level political parties are involved in the local level governance through their elected representatives in both rural and urban forms of local government. Local government in India is a state subject, however, the central government holds a supervisory role to guide, encourage, engage and assist the states to promote local government and development. Political participation in *panchayati raj* elections has a long tradition of great leaders like Jawaharlal Nehru, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel and Subhash Chand Bose who took active leadership in municipal politics. Thus, politics at local government provides a gateway to national level politics and thereby initiates an active involvement of national and regional parties. The presence of national, state and regional parties at the level of local government maintains a strong party presence which has its bearing on national and state level politics. Political parties are the essence of parliamentary democracy and their role in local governments strengthens the roots of democratic decentralization. According to the World

Bank report, in India 65.97 per cent live in rural areas⁵ and 34.03 per cent of the population lives in urban areas.⁶

Local governments have had a tremendous effect in the realization of democracy at the grassroots and at the level of municipalities in the urban areas. Conducting elections at the lowest tier of government has added to the vibrant political culture of India. The trickling down of democratic decentralization and power has entrenched the roots of democracy, however, its substantive realization has many hurdles to cross.

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